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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ACBB	Agroecosystems, Biogeochemical Cycles and Biodiversity (original acronym in French)
C	Carbon
DM	Dry Matter
GHG	Greenhouse gases
LAI	Leaf Area Index
N	Nitrogen
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
TDR	Time Domain Reflectometry
WFPS	Water Filled Pore Space
WP	Work Package

ABSTRACT

This report presents the work carried out to evaluate the STICS model. In ΣOMMIT, STICS will be used to feed – beyond available literature and experimental data – a fuzzy-expert system aiming to assess cropping systems in terms of carbon sequestration potential and trade-offs with GHG emissions and NO₃ leaching. The arable crop component of the ACBB (agroecosystems, biogeochemical cycles and biodiversity) long term experimental network was used for that evaluation. This experiment includes 8 treatments that either allow to compare specific practices or cropping systems, with now 12 years of differentiation. It gives access to most variables of interest to characterize the functioning of the agroecosystem. It is particularly suited to the ΣOMMIT objectives as it includes continuous measurement of N₂O emissions since 2012 and soil organic carbon stock measurements at the start of the experiment and after each rotation. STICS was evaluated with its default set of parameters, as when applied on a site where measurements are not available for specific calibration, in order to approach the predictive capacity of the model when applied to other contexts. Simulations were set up to start in 2009, one year before the beginning of the treatments, and to run continuously until 2021. Results showed that performance in simulating plant growth and soil water dynamics was good, with no apparent bias. Performance in simulating soil mineral nitrogen dynamics was less satisfactory but the range of variation of observed values remained limited as they were obtained at harvest and at the end of winter, i.e. far from fertilization events. Regarding soil organic carbon stock evolution, results were satisfactory for more conventional annual cropping systems, including variations due to residue removal. They highlighted however some limits for the simulation of situations with low N availability or presence of a perennial crop. N₂O emissions simulation results for the conventional management treatment, still without calibration, indicated that the order of magnitude of emissions as well as of peaks was quite good, with some patterns of the temporal dynamics being also well captured. However, cumulative emissions values were overestimated by a factor two. After calibration of the denitrification and nitrification potential values on the conventional management treatment, the model was applied on all other treatments. STICS then simulated quite well the small decrease in N₂O emissions with residue removal and the emissions from the two treatments with reduced mineral nitrogen inputs, with or without legumes to compensate for part the missing nitrogen inputs. It performed also well in simulating N₂O emissions from one of the organic farming treatments and from the treatment with 6 years of switchgrass preceding an annual rotation. However, the model largely failed at simulating N₂O emissions on the second treatment with organic farming, which included two years of alfalfa at the beginning of the rotation. On the whole, STICS performance is considered satisfactory enough to explore additional situations little covered by existing data used by WP5. However, the limits which were brought to light both suggest to delimit carefully the domain for which using the model to explore alternative scenarios is possible, and to continue to improve the model to better deal with these limits.

1. Introduction

This report presents the work carried out by WP4 to evaluate the STICS model. Simulation results from this model (as well as results from the Pasim and Armosa models) will be used to extend the range of information feeding WP5 beyond available literature and experimental data. WP5 focus on the development of a fuzzy-expert system to evaluate carbon sequestration potential and the trade-offs in terms of GHG emissions and NO₃ leaching. Simulation results will allow for WP5 to explore additional situations (climate, soil, management practices) which are little covered by existing data, although of interest for analyzing trade-offs.

It is critical for WP5 to get as soon as possible a typical (although still incomplete) dataset with information coming from literature, long term experiments and simulations, for testing the fuzzy-expert system methodology. It is also an issue that we can start to test options for the setup of the virtual experiments that will feed WP5, as the design of such a numerical experiment is strongly constrained by the exponential growth of the number of simulations with the number of factors aimed to be explored. We thus decided collectively to focus on one long term experiment which already had a solid dataset available (more than 10 years of data, N₂O and soil carbon storage measurements, large panel of agricultural practices) to evaluate the STICS model (new major version just released) especially with regard to N₂O emissions and soil carbon storage, and provide a first set of simulations for WP5. This set of simulations will be extended next by virtual experiments exploring variations in climate, soil and management options.

This report may be updated during the course of the project, to reflect improvements made to the model itself or its parameters set, as the search for improvement in the model continue.

2. Methods

2.1 Dataset used

2.1.1 *The ACBB Long Term Experiment*

The long term experiment used here is the arable crop component of the ACBB (agroecosystems, biogeochemical cycles and biodiversity) network of sites (which also includes a site with temporary grassland in rotation with arable crops, a site with permanent grassland, and a much more recent site with agroforestry). It includes 8 treatments that either allow to compare specific practices or cropping systems. It started in 2010, but treatments T7 and T8 were only added in 2016.

Figure 1 shows the design of the experiment, with a main part and two additional large size plots for eddy-covariance measurements. In the main part, the 6 initial treatments are distributed over 4 blocks. 3 additional blocks have been added for the T7 and T8 treatments. Eddy-covariance measurements are done only on two treatments (T5 and T6). Figure 2 presents the different treatments. There is a conventional management treatment and several variations that allow to study the influence of soil tillage (T2 vs T1), residue management (T3 vs T2), fertilization (T4 vs T1) and rotation of a perennial crop (switchgrass) with annual crops (T6 vs T3). Some of the treatments are less analytical and correspond to more integrated cropping systems: T5 is a cropping system in which we both reduce the mineral nitrogen input (since 2012) and pesticide use (since 2016) by using legumes to fix nitrogen and add diversity into the rotation. T7 and T8 are organic farming treatments which mainly differ by the presence (on T8) or not (on T7) of 2 years of alfalfa at the beginning of the rotation.

Figure 1. Design of the ACBB arable crop long term experiment

Treatment			Surface (ha)	Rotation 2010-2015	Rotation 2016-2021	Soil tillage	Crop residues management	N min fertilization	Inter crops	Legume frequency	Perennial frequency	Chemical protection
T1	CONV	CONventional management	1.61	Pea, Wheat, Rapeseed, Barley, G Maize, Wheat	Pea, Rapeseed, Wheat, Barley, G Maize, Wheat	Annual ploughing	Returned	Reference N	IC no leg	Low	Nil	100%
T2	RT	Reduced Tillage	1.56	Pea, Wheat, Rapeseed, Barley, G Maize, Wheat	Pea, Rapeseed, Wheat, Barley, G Maize, Wheat	Shallow tillage	Returned	Reference N	IC no leg	Low	Nil	100%
T3	RT-RR	Reduced Tillage and Residues Removal	1.63	Pea, Wheat, Rapeseed, Barley, F Maize, Wheat	Pea, Rapeseed, Wheat, Barley, F Maize, Wheat	Shallow tillage	Exported**	Reference N	IC no leg	Low	Nil	100%
T4	RN	Reduced Nitrogen	1.63	Pea, Wheat, Rapeseed, Barley, G Maize, Wheat	Pea, Rapeseed, Wheat, Barley, G Maize, Wheat	Annual ploughing	Returned	35% Reference N	CI non leg	Low	Nil	100%
T5	RN-LEG	Reduced Nitrogen and LEGuminous crops	5.76	Pea, Wheat, Rapeseed, Barley, G Maize, Wheat	Alfalfa, Alfalfa, Wheat, Barley, G Maize, Wheat	Annual ploughing	Returned	35% Reference N	IC leg	High	Nil	30%
T6	RR-PER	Residues Removal and PERennial crops	5.71	Switchgrass (6 years)	Pea, Rapeseed, Wheat, Barley, F Maize, Wheat	Shallow tillage*	Exported**	Reference N	IC no leg	Low	High	100%
T7	OA-T	Organic Agriculture and Tillage	1.27	--	Pea, Asso. Rapeseed, Wheat, Barley, G Maize, Triticale	occasional ploughing	Returned	Nil Legume substitution	Soil Tillage / IC leg	Low	Nil	0%
T8	OA-CC	Organic Agriculture and Cover Crops	1.22	--	Alfalfa, Alfalfa, G Maize, Barley, G Maize, Asso Triticale+field pea	occasional ploughing	Returned	Nil Legume substitution	IC leg	High	Nil	0%
T3_SN	BS	Perennial bare soil	0.005	Pea, Wheat, Rapeseed, Barley, F Maize, Wheat	perennial bare soil	Shallow tillage	No résidues introduction	Reference N	None	None	None	100%

* Ploughed once after switchgrass
 ** Except after rapeseed crop

Figure 2. ACBB long term experiment treatments

The experiment has now reach 12 years of differentiation between treatments. It is particularly suited to the Σ OMMIT objectives as it includes continuous measurement of N_2O emissions since 2012 and soil organic carbon stock measurements at the start of the experiment and after each rotation (see section 2.1.2).

2.1.2 Main measurements

Since the beginning of the experiment, a lot of variables are measured to characterize the functioning of the studied agroecosystem, among which:

- variables related to the crops (biomass, yield, LAI, N and C content, ...);
- variables related to the physical state of the soil (bulk density, soil water content, soil temperature, ...) or soil mineral or organic components content (NH_4 , NO_3 , organic carbon and nitrogen);
- fluxes variables such as evapotranspiration, drainage, N leaching, N_2O emissions, C fluxes, ...

All of these variables are of interest for testing models, either because they are direct or indirect control variables of the processes of interest, or are directly measurements of the processes of interest.

Of particular interest for the Σ OMMIT project are the soil organic carbon stock measurements and N_2O emission measurements.

Soil organic carbon stocks

Soil organic carbon stocks were measured on all treatments (and all plots) at the beginning of the experiment in 2009 (initial characterization before the setup of treatments), in 2015 after the first rotation, and in 2021 after the second rotation (with support from the Σ OMMIT project). Result are only available at that moment from the first two campaigns.

Soil organic carbon stock measurements were done using a systematic sampling scheme (initial grid with 8 measurements per plot on average for the main part of the experiment, complemented by several transects with much closer measurements to estimate short distance spatial structure). Sampling (both bulk density and carbon content) was done over 60 cm with different layers, and the equivalent soil mass approach was used to calculate stocks. This is important because calculating stocks at fixed depth can lead to significant misinterpretation of data when soil bulk density changes trough time. In addition, using georeferenced sampling points with resampling close to the points of the previous campaign allow to have a much better precision on the estimation of soil carbon stock evolution by taking into account the initial variability of the carbon content in soil.

N_2O measurements

N_2O measurements are done using automatic chambers of large size (0.7 m x 0.7 m), which is important for being more representative and smooth short distance spatial variability (Figure 3 and Figure 4). The chambers are distributed into sets of six chambers, each set connected to two infrared gas analyzers: one for CO_2 (LI-COR Biosciences, LI-820) and the other for N_2O (Thermo Environmental Instruments, 46C or 46i).

Figure 3. Automatic chamber for N_2O emissions measurement

Figure 4. N_2O measurement setup: 2 x 3 chambers connected to one analyzer

Measurements are done continuously over the long term, with 4 measurements per 24h during 20 min. Figure 5 shows the timeline of N_2O emissions measurements from the beginning of the experiment to now, for each plot and treatment. It illustrates the strong intensification of measurements with time, which allowed:

- to progressively monitor all treatments;
- to progressively include true replicates, i.e. replications not only inside a given plot for a given treatment (which are maintained because it is not possible to distribute freely chambers due to cables length constraints) but in different plots distributed into different blocks for each treatment. This is very important if we want to derive conclusions on the effect of treatments without the risk of observing confounding effects (although the soil is very homogeneous on the site).

Figure 5. Timeline of N_2O emissions measurements. One line = one plot, one color = one treatment, thickness is proportional to the number of chambers (generally 3 in one plot)

Because results will be visible when compared to simulations (see section 3), we do not present results here, except for two illustrations of the interest of having long term measurements and true replicates for N_2O emissions.

2.1.3 Criticality of long term measurements with true replicates for N_2O emissions

Figure 6 shows the cumulative difference in N_2O emissions between some pairs of treatments. If the treatment has no effect, we should have a horizontal line remaining at 0 as there is no difference. It is interesting to focus on 3 different cases:

- Reduced fertilization (T4 - T1). As there is less emissions when fertilization is reduced, values are negative, and the more time passes, the more the cumulative difference is negative, with an effect which is already present right from the beginning of the experiment, and seems constant in time. This is the simplest case, and we can imagine that in such a situation, this is not that important to wait for long term differentiation of treatments, or measuring during a long period of time. Whatever the moment, measurements during a couple of years would have brought the same conclusion.
- Residue removal (T3 - T2). In that case, it took a few years for a differentiation to become visible, then during several years the tendency was to have a little bit less N_2O emissions with residue removal, which is expected as this conducts to N and C substrate limitation. However recent years again show little difference if any between the two treatments. Here, long term measurements are necessary to capture the complexity of the temporal dynamics of differentiation while long term results seem however consistent with the initial trend.
- Reduced tillage (T2 - T1). Here the temporal dynamics of differentiation shows no durable trend. There are continuous changes in the treatments effects, sometimes reduced tillage leading to higher emissions, sometimes to lower emissions. It would be very dangerous to conclude from limited measurement periods.

Figure 6. Cumulative difference in N₂O emissions between pairs of treatments that allow to analyze the effect of a management practice

Another important point is illustrated by Figure 7. In that case the issue is not only how much N₂O emissions are spatially variable, but overall how the effect of the treatments itself may be variable depending on where the measurements are done. We can see that after an initial period where there is little differentiation between the treatments, in a consistent manner whatever the block considered, the final period shows very contrasted results: depending on the block on which measurement are done, we may conclude that residue removal increases emissions, or that it decreases emissions, or even that it has no effect. Comparing two plots with different management practices or cropping systems is something that is not rare in the literature, and which has clear limits in terms of interpretation. True replicates allowing to manage confounding effect or simple strong spatial variability are very useful to manage that difficulty.

Figure 7. Cumulative difference between two treatments (T2 and T3) for 3 different blocks from the ACBB LTE

2.2 Simulations with STICS

2.2.1 Overview of the model

The soil-crop model STICS (Brisson et al., 1998, 2002, 2008) is a one-dimensional daily time-step model which simulates plant growth as well as water, C and N cycles over one or several growing seasons. It considers several soil layers with specific properties and uses pedoclimatic characteristics and management practices as inputs for the simulations. The description of the physical and biological processes occurring in the soil-crop system mostly relies on a set of generic parameters which are considered not specific of a context of study and thus are not subject to any calibration. This reduces the risk of introducing bias through specific calibration which often relies on limited or uncertain data when comparing scenarios over a range of contexts. Coucheney et al. (2015) evaluated the ability of the STICS model to simulate different plant, water and nitrogen outputs over a wide range of pedoclimatic conditions and N fertilization rates in France. Despite the large diversity of conditions considered and the use of the standard set of model parameters, simulated results were shown to be good enough to allow useful predictions of crop and soil variables when the objective is to compare a variety of pedoclimatic and agronomic situations.

The simulation of N₂O emissions in STICS relies on the concepts described in Bessou et al. (2010). Nitrification and denitrification processes, and the N₂O emissions associated to each process, are simulated separately. Coupling of nitrification and denitrification exists through the production of nitrate by nitrification, which then serves as substrate for denitrification and N₂O emissions associated to this pathway. Processes are described using a functional approach which is similar to that used in other models like DayCent or Ecosse. Nitrification rate is considered to be proportional to NH₄⁺ content, which proved to be a good approximation over the typical range of ammonium content in soil. It is affected by temperature, increasing until an optimum rate at 32.5°C and then decreasing again (Benoit et al., 2015). Water filled pore space (WFPS) strongly influences the rate of nitrification: nitrification increases until field capacity is reached, then decreases because of the decline of soil aeration (Khalil et al., 2004). The soil pH also constrains nitrification rate, which is nil below a pH value of 4 and maximal above a pH value of 7. N₂O emission associated to the nitrification pathway is calculated as a variable fraction of the nitrification rate. That fraction remains low for WFPS values below 60% (0.16–0.29%) but strongly increase with WFPS afterwards to reach a maximum of 2.56% at 100% WFPS as a consequence of the resulting decline in oxygen availability (Khalil et al., 2004). Denitrification is calculated as the product of a soil dependent potential rate and functions expressing the effects of nitrate concentration, soil temperature and soil water content. Denitrification rate increases with nitrate content following a Michaelis-Menten kinetics with a half maximum constant of 148 mg NO₃-N/L (Bessou et al., 2010). Denitrification rate also increases with temperature over most of the typical range of temperature as the optimum rate is 47°C (Benoit et al., 2015). As in the NEMIS model (Hénault and Germon, 2000), denitrification rate is null when WFPS is below a threshold which default value is 62% and then increases exponentially with WFPS. N₂O emission from denitrification is calculated as a variable fraction of the denitrification rate which mainly depends on pH and WFPS. Acid pH strongly inhibits N₂O reduction to N₂ (Rochester, 2003). In the model, the N₂O end-product ratio of denitrification increases with pH decreasing from 9.2 to 5.6. For pH values below 6, denitrification has N₂O as main end-product. Finally, soil water content values close to saturation favor N₂O reduction to N₂. This is due to the development of anoxia (Vieten et al., 2008) and to the increase in the residence time of N₂O into the soil associated to lower gaseous diffusion rates. This effect is taken into account through a linear decrease of the denitrification end-product ratio between the threshold WFPS for the onset of denitrification and maximal soil saturation (Bessou et al., 2010).

In STICS, the biological activity and thus the soil organic carbon mineralization is assumed to occur only in the topsoil to a maximum depth called *profhum* (e.g. 30 cm). Four pools of organic carbon and nitrogen are simulated in the soil: organic inputs (organic fertilizers and crop residues), microbial biomass, active soil organic matter (called “humus”) and inert soil organic matter. The decomposition of the first three pools follows a first-order kinetics, with a potential decomposition rate modulated by the environmental conditions, particularly soil temperature and soil water content. Substrate decomposition results in C mineralization (CO₂ emission) and microbial assimilation depending on a microbial yield rate. N fluxes (immobilization and mineralization) are driven by C fluxes and the C:N ratio of the organic pools. The parameters of the organic residues decomposition module have been calibrated using long-term incubations in the laboratory (Justes et al., 2009). The decomposition rate of organic residues can be limited by lack of mineral N, as well as the N immobilization process. The decomposition rate of the active pool depends on soil properties (clay, organic N and CaCO₃ contents, pH and C:N ratio), as established by Clivot et al. (2017) and climate (soil temperature and water content). The proportion of stable SOC varies with crop history from 40% under permanent grassland to 65% under permanent arable cropping.

The STICS model here evaluated is the new version 10, which has just been released. It was significantly improved for carbon cycling and better taking into account roots as a carbon source and perennials crops. The ability of STICS v10 to simulate soil organic carbon and nitrogen stock evolution has previously been tested in a rather large range of situations (Autret et al., 2020; Clivot et al., 2020; Yin et al., 2020).

2.2.2 Model evaluation strategy

As already stated in section 2.2.1, we consider that model parameters should be as much as possible generic so as to preserve the predictive capacity of the model when applied to other contexts. This reduces the risk of introducing bias through site specific calibration which often relies on limited or uncertain data (Coucheney et al., 2015). We thus first evaluated the model using the default parameters set (no calibration), as when applied on any different site. Input values (soil properties, climate, nature of the crop, management operations) were carefully filled in for each of the 8 treatments and separately for the two large plots with eddy-covariance measurements as they are a few hundred meters apart.

Simulations were set up to start in 2009, one year before the installation of treatments, and to run continuously until 2021. The soil profile was described over 210 cm with 5 layers (which is a limit of STICS). The top layer, which is of particular interest for the simulation of N₂O emissions, was 30 cm depth.

Both scatterplots and temporal dynamics of simulated versus observed variables will be presented, with a focus on N₂O emissions, carbon stocks and the effect of management practices, as this is the scope of the ΣOMMIT project and a general and comprehensive evaluation on a multi-sites database is already done when each new version of the model is released.

3. Model evaluation results without calibration

3.1 Control variables

We will first focus on variables that directly or indirectly influence N₂O emission processes and carbon storage: plant growth for example influences the state of water in the soil through transpiration, or

mineral nitrogen availability through N uptake. Soil water is particularly important for N₂O emissions as it controls microbial activity but also oxygen availability by constraining air diffusion into the profile.

3.1.1 Aboveground biomass and yield

Figure 8. Simulated versus observed crop aboveground biomass. Different colors correspond to different crops.

Figure 8 shows simulated versus observed plant aboveground biomass for all treatments and crops. Colors are used to differentiate crops. Overall performance is quite good, with no apparent bias, except for the largest biomass values which are slightly overestimated. The model thus seems quite capable of estimating plant biomass production over a large range of crops. When we look at each crop separately, performances are less satisfying, with some dispersion occurring (spring barley for example). However, for wheat for example the model is still capable to capture variations in biomass production over a range of 8 to more than 20 t DM/ha.

As shown in Figure 9, yield is also globally well predicted, although a little less well than plant biomass, especially for spring barley (for which yields are underestimated by STICS).

Figure 9. Simulated versus observed crop yield. Different colors correspond to different crops.

Part of the difficulty to simulate plant biomass and yield is probably associated to the fact that plant files corresponding to the specific variety used are not always available. That may be improved in the future, but remains an issue as diversification is more and more taking place which put a strong challenge on plant file calibration for specific cultivars.

3.1.2 Soil water

Evapotranspiration is a major driver of soil water dynamics, and strongly dependent on the good prediction of plant growth. The flux tower available for the treatment T5 on one of the large plot allows to measure evapotranspiration and to compare it to the simulated values. Data are available since 2018 (and for the moment only for the flux tower on T5). Figure 10 shows the dynamics of observed and simulated evapotranspiration. Both the order of magnitude and the temporal dynamics are very well predicted.

Figure 10. Simulated (grey points) and observed (red points) evapotranspiration dynamics.

Simulated versus observed soil water content for the more superficial soil layer (0-30 cm) are shown in Figure 11. There is a good agreement between simulated values and observed values over a large range of soil water content values. Only gravimetric measurements are shown here, which are more reliable, and not values derived from TDR probe measurements. The absence of variations of simulated values for the wettest conditions is due to the tipping bucket nature of soil water transfer in STICS: soil water content drains to deeper layer as soon as field capacity is reached, which is why simulated soil water content cannot exceed field capacity (while it is possible in the field). There is however a special option that allows to consider saturation rates above field capacity in the nitrification and denitrification routines and its influence on N₂O emission processes for days with rainfall, but outputs are not visible.

Figure 11. Simulated versus observed soil water content (0-30 cm). Different colors correspond to different treatments.

Soil water stock over 150 cm is also well predicted, with almost no bias (Figure 12). This is important for ensuring good prediction of plant growth.

Figure 12. Simulated versus observed soil water stock (0-150 cm).

Results regarding prediction of soil temperature, especially for the superficial layer, are not presented because they are very good and the very small differences between predicted values and observed values are not likely to induce significant deviations in the prediction of N₂O emissions.

3.1.3 Soil mineral nitrogen

Soil mineral nitrogen, both in ammonium and nitrate form, is a very important control variable for N₂O emissions. Ammonium is the main N substrate for nitrification, while nitrate is the N substrate for denitrification. Regarding N₂O emissions, it is mineral nitrogen content in the soil surface layer which is critical.

Figure 13 shows simulated versus observed values of nitrate content in the 0-30 cm soil layer for the different treatments. Performances are less good than for other variables. However, the range of variation of nitrate content is quite limited as these data correspond to mineral nitrogen measurements done at harvest and at the end of winter, *i.e.* quite far from fertilization events.

Figure 13. Simulated versus observed soil nitrate content (0-30 cm). Different colors correspond to different treatments.

That is illustrated on Figure 14, which shows the simulated dynamics together with the available measured values. There are no measurement corresponding to peaks of nitrate content at fertilization or in the following weeks due to nitrification of ammonium. Cover crops such as mustard seems to contribute significantly to the mismatch between simulated and observed values. We can also observe a strong underestimation of the nitrate content of the 0-30 cm layer for the T8 treatment in 2018, which corresponds to a period following two years of alfalfa.

Figure 14: Simulated (lines) and observed (points) soil nitrate content dynamics (0-30 cm) for different treatments

The same analysis can be done for ammonium (Figure 15): the range of values measured is very limited, which results in mainly dispersion being observed when comparing simulated values to observed values. How the range of observed values is limited compared to simulated values (which include fertilization events) is apparent on the temporal dynamics graph for T1 included in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Simulated versus observed soil ammonium content (0-30 cm). Different colors correspond to different treatments. The temporal dynamics shown corresponds to the conventional treatment.

3.2 Soil carbon stocks

Simulated soil organic carbon dynamics (0-35 cm stock) is shown in Figure 16 together with already available soil carbon stock measurements (2010 and 2015). The soil organic carbon stock at the beginning of the simulation for each treatment is imposed.

Figure 16. Simulated (lines) and observed (points) dynamics of soil organic carbon stocks for different treatments.

For the T1 and T2 treatments (conventional management, with or without plowing), observations indicate no significant change in soil carbon stocks between the two campaigns, which is also what is shown by simulations despite variations through time. This confirms the ability of STICS to simulate soil organic carbon stock evolution, at least for conventional annual cropping systems, in various pedoclimatic conditions (Clivot et al., 2020). However, for T2, at the moment of the second measurement, the simulation seems to slightly underestimate the carbon stock.

In the T3 treatment, residue removal induces a decrease of soil carbon stock through time during the first rotation, which is in agreement with simulations. The simulation suggests a slowing of this decrease during the second rotation, which has to be confirmed.

In treatments T4 and T5, the strong reduction in mineral fertilization (although for part compensated by biological N fixation in T5) results in a decrease in carbon stocks, due to less biomass produced and returned to the soil. This decrease is more pronounced on T5 due to the higher initial stock. The simulation quite well reproduces the dynamics on T5, however it fails at reproducing the decrease in soil carbon stock on T4. This is not a priori related to bad prediction of plant biomass as we saw they were quite good, but the lack of nitrogen could also have a more direct effect on carbon storage through stoichiometry constraints, which is not simulated. It can also be noted that large decrease in simulated soil carbon stock seems to be only observed in situations with higher initial carbon stocks, which is not the case for T4 and may induce a difficulty in simulating the observed decrease. Measurements done in 2021 will allow to consolidate the analysis.

Finally, on treatment T6, observations show an increase in soil carbon storage, which is observed before the destruction of the switchgrass (which was grown continuously from spring 2010 to autumn 2015). STICS simulates an increase in soil carbon storage of the same order of magnitude, but later, after destruction of the crop. That suggests that the observed increase may be gradual, for example associated to carbon released by roots, while the simulated increase seems more associated to the returning of a large mass of carbon to the soil (rhizomes, roots and aboveground residues) at the destruction of the crop. That will be very interesting to analyze in more details and may help to improve the model in the case of perennial crop cultivation.

3.3 N₂O emissions

3.3.1 Evaluation using default values for model parameters

Evaluation of the model for N₂O emissions will first be done focusing on the conventional management treatment. Only later we will go through the different treatments and the capacity of the model to reproduce the effect of agricultural practices or cropping systems.

Figure 17 shows the simulated and observed N₂O emissions dynamics for the conventional treatment. Simulation begins before the setup of treatments, in 2009, while observations only began later. For simulation, the contribution of nitrification and denitrification to N₂O emissions is distinguished. The simulation is done without any calibration, even for the denitrification potential whose default value is an average from measurements done at several places in northern France (2 kg N/ha/day for 20 cm of soil). Actually denitrification could be considered as a soil dependent parameter, as it varies depending on the soil (and also in time although this is not considered in STICS for the moment). However, it is quite difficult to measure and can vary over orders of magnitude depending on the measurement method used.

Figure 17. Simulated (pink lines) and observed (blue points) N_2O emissions dynamics for the conventional treatment (T1). For simulations, the contribution of nitrification and denitrification to N_2O emissions is distinguished.

We can see that the order of magnitude of emissions as well as of peaks is quite good. This is also interesting to observe that some patterns of the temporal dynamics are also well captured. However, looking at cumulative emissions (Figure 18) indicates that the model overestimate by a factor 2 total emissions for this treatment, which is not that bad considering the absence of calibration but nevertheless not satisfying. We will go into a more detailed analysis by first looking at simulated emissions originating from nitrification (Figure 19).

Figure 18. Simulated (pink) and observed (blue) cumulative N_2O emissions for the conventional treatment.

Figure 19. Simulated (pink lines) and observed (blue points) N_2O emissions dynamics for the conventional treatment with denitrification contribution forced to 0.

Again, the good representation of some temporal dynamics patterns is well apparent. This is especially the case at the beginning of the observation period. The good agreement between simulated emissions from nitrification only and observed total N_2O emissions suggests that nitrification may be dominant in the production of N_2O , which is not surprising on the site, which has well-draining soils and a small carbon content. Looking at cumulative values (Figure 20) indicates that observed total N_2O emissions and simulated emissions coming from nitrification are pretty close.

Figure 20. Simulated (pink) and observed (blue) cumulative N_2O emissions for the conventional treatment with denitrification contribution forced to 0.

However, it remains that while cumulative values are very similar, some observed peaks are missed which may be due to active denitrification in the field. That suggests denitrification contribution is needed to simulated the observed emissions, especially for peaks, while nitrification contribution is major but overestimated.

On Figure 21 we have underlined in green the periods for which activating denitrification results in an improvement of the simulated emissions. That corresponds to periods where denitrification is needed

and explains well large N₂O peaks. However, there are also periods underlined in red where either activating denitrification results in strong overestimation of the peaks (first and second red boxes), or does not help at all to simulate an observed peak (third red box).

Figure 21. Simulated (pink lines) and observed (blue points) N₂O emissions dynamics for the conventional treatment. For simulations, the contribution of nitrification and denitrification to N₂O emissions is distinguished. Green boxes indicate periods where activating denitrification strongly improves N₂O emissions peaks prediction. On the contrary red boxes underline periods where either denitrification activation results in a strong overestimation of N₂O emissions or has no effect to improve peak emission predictions.

This highlights at the same time how the model and the simulation of both nitrification and denitrification processes does a good job for predicting N₂O emissions, and how limits to our modelling capacity persist, calling for further improvement.

3.3.2 Simulation of different treatments

Before analyzing how the STICS model behaves in simulating the effect of the different treatments on N₂O emissions, we tried to make some corrections in parameters values to improve performances in the conventional management treatment (T1). Based on what we learnt from the previous analysis on this treatment, we considered that we have to keep some contribution of denitrification, and reduce the contribution of nitrification which is probably less than 100%. The denitrification potential was changed from the default value to a value of 0.7 kg/ha/day, which is pretty close to the value of 0.9 kg/ha/day we estimated in Bessou et al. (2010), and the potential proportion of ammonium nitrified each day was decreased to get cumulative simulated emission values consistent with the observed one. This quick adjustment of two parameters allowed to get correct cumulative emissions over the whole period of measurement as well as better representation of the dynamics and peaks. Then we kept these parameters and ran again the simulation for the other treatments without any change.

Results are shown in Figure 22 for the temporal dynamics, and Figure 23 for the cumulative values. On top is the T1 conventional management treatment on which this simple calibration was done.

Figure 22. Simulated (pink lines) and observed (blue points) N_2O emissions dynamics for the different treatments. A calibration of denitrification and nitrification potential has been done on the conventional management treatment. The same parameter set has been applied without change to the other treatments.

Figure 23. Simulated (pink) and observed (blue) cumulative N₂O emissions for the different treatments. A calibration of denitrification and nitrification potential has been done on the conventional management treatment. The same parameter set has been applied without change to the other treatments.

There is little to say about the temporal dynamics as it is difficult to see the effect of the treatments. Cumulative values are more informative. We can see that application of the model calibrated on the conventional treatment (T1) allows to simulate quite well the two treatments with reduced mineral nitrogen inputs (T4 and T5), one of them (T5) including legumes to partially compensate the missing nitrogen inputs. Furthermore, the model performed also well in simulating N₂O emissions from one of the organic farming treatments (T7) and from the treatment with 6 years of switchgrass preceding an annual rotation (T6), which is good as the drivers of emissions and part of the crops are different in these more complex cropping systems. Emissions are not much affected by suppressing deep ploughing (T2 vs T1) and by removing residues (T3 vs T2), which is also what is predicted by the model, which accurately simulates the small decrease in N₂O emissions with residue removal (T3 vs T2). However, the model largely failed at simulating N₂O emissions on the second treatment with organic farming (T8 with 2 years of alfalfa), in particular due to the inability to simulate a limited period with very high emission after alfalfa was harvested and the remaining biomass, including roots, returned to the soil. This period also corresponds to an underestimation of the nitrate content in the surface layer (Figure 14).

4. Conclusions and perspectives

Results from this evaluation of the STICS model against the ACBB dataset allow to draw the following conclusions:

- The ACBB dataset is quite unique in the duration, continuity, frequency of N₂O emission measurement, combined to the coverage of a wide range of agricultural practices. It also provides solid measurements of soil organic carbon stocks and their evolution and follow-up of numerous variables of interest to understand N₂O emission temporal dynamics. It then qualifies as a very relevant dataset to highlight model performances as well as their limits, whether regarding the ability to simulate temporal dynamics of N₂O emissions or how these emissions or the trade-off with soil organic carbon storage respond to changes in management practices. It has however quite low levels of N₂O emissions compared to other sites in the literature, which is for a large part related to high pH values which favor reduction of N₂O to N₂ and probably also to a low contribution of denitrification to emissions.
- Overall performances of the model are quite good even with no or very limited calibration. In particular, the model does not suffer strong limits in simulating crop growth, which is a strong drivers of N availability, or soil water dynamics which strongly influence N₂O emissions. This is more difficult to conclude about mineral nitrogen dynamics as observations are available mainly for periods of low N availability. These good performances with limited calibration are important as they suggest that there is no need for strong site specific calibration, which is better if we want to preserve the genericity of the model and its ability to be applied to different contexts.
- There are however periods and even treatments for which simulation results are completely out of it (whether it be for N₂O emissions, soil organic carbon storage or trade-offs between the two). In depth analysis of simulated vs observed dynamics (which is permitted by the high measurement frequency on the ACBB experiment) is a very good way to point where we seem to understand the processes at play and where we have to improve. This is for example the case for some N₂O emissions peaks which are completely missed. One of the best example is the large emission peak after the two years of alfalfa on T8 which results in strongly underestimated cumulated emissions and seems to be associated at least for part to the

underestimation of nitrate produced by decomposition-mineralization of alfalfa. Failure at simulating soil organic carbon stock evolution on the treatment with low fertilization (with no legumes to compensate, T4) and on the treatment with 6 years of switchgrass are also indications of weaknesses of the model in taking into account stoichiometric constraints on carbon stabilization in N limited situations, or predominant continuous C input to the soil by roots when perennial crops are present.

On the whole, STICS performances remain satisfactory enough to consider exploring additional situations (climate, soil, management practices) which are little covered by existing data used by WP5. However, the limits which were brought to light both suggest to delimit carefully the domain for which using the model to explore alternative scenarios is possible, and to continue to improve the model to better deal with these limits. Regarding these improvements, we think that there is probably more to gain from going deeper into result analysis for the ACBB long term experiment than to multiply the datasets used. Such a deep analysis of model performance (which was missing in model intercomparison studies) is only possible when the dataset is sufficiently rich, and it is furthermore limited by the difficulty of considering numerous sites. However, we will consider extending the dataset used to at least a site where conditions are more favorable to denitrification and where the pH is lower and limits reduction of N₂O to N₂, so as to check if satisfactory performances still hold with different contribution of nitrification and denitrification and more intensive emissions.

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